

TABLE 1

Chelates	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)						Δ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$
			M	C	H	N	S	Cl	
[Zn(TBHNH) ₂]Cl ₂	Dull white	215	11.28 (11.25)	51.49 (51.47)	2.77 (2.82)	9.89 (9.83)	11.11 (11.00)	12.32 (12.28)	129
[Cd(TBHN) ₂]	Yellow	200	20.28 (20.20)	43.47 (43.49)	2.89 (1.58)	10.14 (10.00)	11.55 (11.50)	—	8
[Hg(TBHN) ₂]	Reddish brown	270	31.38 (31.29)	37.47 (37.41)	2.49 (1.38)	8.73 (8.62)	9.98 (9.92)	—	8.5

In the ir spectra of Zn^{II} chelate the ν_{NH} band of the ligand remained unaffected while in Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chelates it disappeared. This obviously shows that unlike in Zn^{II} chelate, coordination occurs through deprotonated nitrogen in Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chelates. In the spectra of Zn^{II} chelate, a very strong band appears at 1705 cm⁻¹ with a weak shoulder at 1690 cm⁻¹, which shows that C = O of C₆H₅ C = O has taken part in coordination. In the spectra of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chelates, there is no marked change in the $\nu_{C=O}$, which shows that carbonyl groups are free. The band at 1450 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C-S}) in the free ligand, however, is shifted to lower frequency in all the three chelates. It shows that sulphur is coordinated in all the three chelates. Coordination through oxygen and sulphur in Zn^{II} chelate may further be substantiated by the appearance of two bands at 545 (M—O) and 315 cm⁻¹ (M—S). The non-electrolytic nature of Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} chelates confirms coordination through deprotonated nitrogen.

Tetrahedral structure is suggested to all the three chelates as it is the most preferred geometry for a d¹⁰ system.

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Potentiometric Studies of some Mixed Ligand Chelates of Samarium(III) with Phenolic Hydroxy Compounds as Secondary Ligands

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RECENTLY, there has been considerable interest on the studies of mixed ligand complexes of lanthanides by pH-metric methods¹⁻⁴. The importance of mixed ligand complexes in environmental chemistry⁵, medicinal chemistry⁶, analytical chemistry⁷ and industrial chemistry⁸ has led to large number of reports on the formation and stabilities of mixed ligand complexes⁹. The rare earth ions^{1,10,11} expand their coordination number more than commonly assumed six.

In the present paper an attempt has been made to study $\log K_{MAL}^{M^3A}$ of Sm^{III} systems, where M = Sm^{III}; A = nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA), N-hydroxyethylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA), ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), cyclohexanediaminetetraacetic acid (CDTA); and L = hydroquinone (HQ), 1-hydroxynaphthaic acid (1-HNA), 3-hydroxynaphthaic acid (3-HNA), and alizarin red S (ARS). The stability constants at 25 and 35°, and at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M \text{ NaClO}_4$), have been determined employing a modified form of Irving and Rossotti¹² potentiometric titration technique.

Experimental

A stock solution (0.01 M) of samarium perchlorate was prepared in calculated quantity of perchloric acid and its metal content was estimated by spectrophotometric method¹³. Solutions of 0.05 M each of NTA (B.D.H.), HEDTA (Sigma), Na₂EDTA (Sigma) and CDTA (Kochlight) and 0.01 M each of HQ and ARS (Loba-chemie) were prepared in double distilled water; 0.01 M each of 1-HNA and 3-HNA (Loba-chemie) were prepared in purified alcohol. All the solutions were stan-

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standardised potentiometrically. A Systronics 335 digital pH meter with accuracy ± 0.01 units was used for pH measurements. The temperature was maintained by immersing the cell in a thermostat having accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. For the study of mixed-ligand complexes, following four mixtures were prepared: (A) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid, (B) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand, (C) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Sm^{III} solution + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand, and (D) $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ perchloric acid + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Sm^{III} solution + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ secondary ligand. The ionic strength was maintained to $0.1 M$ by adding appropriate amount of neutral NaClO_4 . The mixtures were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide ($1.260 M$) using pH meter. A typical plot of pH against volume have been presented in Fig. 1 for Sm^{III} -(CDTA)-(1-HNA) system at 25° .

Fig. 1. Titration curves for Sm^{III} -(CDTA)-(1-HNA) system at 25° : (O) acid, (●) secondary ligand, (▲) primary complex and (△) ternary complex.

The values \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated as described earlier³. The values obtained for 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants for secondary ligands used are recorded in Table 1.

A typical plot of \bar{n} vs pL for $[\text{Sm}^{III}$ -(CDTA)-(HQ)] is shown in Fig. 2. The values for mixed ligand chelate stability constants obtained are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SECONDARY LIGANDS

Ligand	Constant	Temp., $^\circ\text{C}$	
		25°	35°
1-HNA*	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{1}{2}}^H$	10.60	10.49
	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{2}{2}}^H$	2.60	2.51
3-HNA*	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{1}{2}}^H$	10.50	10.38
	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{2}{2}}^H$	2.40	2.32
ARS	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{1}{2}}^H$	11.00	10.91
	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{2}{2}}^H$	5.70	5.53
HQ	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{1}{2}}^H$	8.70	8.62
	$\text{Log } K_{\frac{2}{2}}^H$	5.50	5.42

*Experiments in ethanol-water (1 : 1) medium.

TABLE 2 METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS ($\text{log } K_{ML}^{MA}$)

System	Temp., $^\circ\text{C}$	
	25°	35°
$[\text{Sm}(\text{NTA})(1\text{-HNA})]^*$	5.00	4.82
$[\text{Sm}(\text{NTA})(3\text{-HNA})]^*$	4.82	4.68
$[\text{Sm}(\text{NTA})(\text{ARS})]$	5.02	4.78
$[\text{Sm}(\text{NTA})(\text{HQ})]$	5.20	5.00
$[\text{Sm}(\text{EDTA})(1\text{-HNA})]^*$	6.00	5.85
$[\text{Sm}(\text{EDTA})(3\text{-HNA})]^*$	5.90	5.72
$[\text{Sm}(\text{EDTA})(\text{ARS})]$	5.42	5.23
$[\text{Sm}(\text{EDTA})(\text{HQ})]$	5.50	5.34
$[\text{Sm}(\text{HEDTA})(1\text{-HNA})]^*$	4.90	4.70
$[\text{Sm}(\text{HEDTA})(3\text{-HNA})]^*$	4.98	4.76
$[\text{Sm}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{ARS})]$	5.00	4.88
$[\text{Sm}(\text{HEDTA})(\text{HQ})]$	5.01	4.89
$[\text{Sm}(\text{CDTA})(1\text{-HNA})]^*$	6.30	6.12
$[\text{Sm}(\text{CDTA})(3\text{-HNA})]^*$	6.20	6.01
$[\text{Sm}(\text{CDTA})(\text{ARS})]$	6.41	6.23
$[\text{Sm}(\text{CDTA})(\text{HQ})]$	6.25	6.10

*Experiments in ethanol-water (1 : 1) medium.

Fig. 2. Formation curves of Sm^{III} -(CDTA)-(HQ) system at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) and at different temperatures: (●) 25° and (O) 35° .

The order of stability constants of mixed ligand chelates with the change in secondary ligands is $HQ > 1-HNA > 3-HNA > ARS$. This can be explained on the basis of size of these ligands. The bulkier ligand attachment to primary complex will be steriospecifically hindered and will destabilise the complex. The order of stability constants of mixed ligand chelates with respect to primary ligands is

$$K_{MAL}^{NTA} > K_{MAL}^{HEDTA} > K_{MAL}^{EDTA} > K_{MAL}^{CDTA}$$

The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ show that the stability of these mixed ligand chelates decreases with the increase in temperature. All the secondary ligands act as bidentate and effective coordination number for samarium(III) in these species is six, seven and eight in the case of NTA, HEDTA, EDTA = CDTA, respectively. From the results it can be suggested that the coordination number of samarium can be expanded more than six.

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Polarographic Behaviour of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents *vis-a-vis* Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of nitroacetanilides in aqueous mixtures of inert organic solvents *vis-a-vis* kinetics of the electrode reaction has not been studied so far. Hence, the title study has been undertaken in aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, propanol, butanol and dimethylformamide.

Experimental

ortho-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides (B.D.H.) were recrystallised from ethanol before use. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The concentration of each depolariser was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Desired concentrations of various constituents of BR buffer of pH 6.1 were added to the solution to be polarographed. $NaNO_3$ (0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal PL 02 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S. C. E.). The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction of the nitroacetanilides was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹. It gave the value of n equal to 4 for each depolariser at pH 6.1. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion coefficient of nitroacetanilides in the presence of aqueous mixtures of organic solvents. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{f,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky's method^{2,3}. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$ were calculated⁴ from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.s.}$. Throughout the measurements current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{5,6}. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m=2.71 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t=3.4 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.38 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ (in 0.1 M $NaNO_3$, open circuit); $h_{oorr} = 32.3 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

ortho-, *meta*- and *para*-Nitroacetanilides yield a single well-defined wave (pH 6.1) in the presence of increasing percentage of different organic solvents. The waves become drawn out at higher percentages of propanol and DMF. The reduction of each depolariser is diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the fact that the plots of i_d vs $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$ are linear and pass through the origin. Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of the nitroacetanilides in the presence of increasing percentages of organic solvents were applied. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a 4-electron reversible reduction process. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of the nitroacetanilides is irreversible^{5,6}. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{6,7} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on h_{oorr} at different stages of the wave was also studied. It was found that the current was independent of h_{oorr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{oorr}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave.